

Orbital Alveolar Rhabdomyosarcoma in A 26-Year-Old Woman At 23 Weeks Gestation: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Alveolar orbital rhabdomyosarcoma is a rare malignant neoplasm in adults and even more uncommon during pregnancy, characterized by aggressive behavior and poor prognosis. We present the case of a 26-year-old woman at 23 weeks of gestation with progressive proptosis, diplopia, and decreased visual acuity. Magnetic resonance imaging revealed an expansive orbital lesion, histologically confirmed as alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma. Management required a multidisciplinary approach, prioritizing maternal-fetal stability while establishing an appropriate oncologic therapeutic strategy. This case discusses the challenges in diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of pregnant patients with orbital tumors, highlighting the importance of individualized strategies and evidence-based protocols to optimize clinical outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, orbital tumor, malignant neoplasm, soft tissue sarcoma, pregnancy and cancer, ocular oncology and case report.

ABBREVIATIONS: Rhabdomyosarcoma (RMS), computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), World Health Organization (WHO), Intergroup Rhabdomyosarcoma Study Group (IRSG), overall survival (SG), radiotherapy (RT).

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INTRODUCTION

Rhabdomyosarcoma (RMS) is a malignant tumor derived from mesenchymal cells capable of differentiating into striated muscle. It is the most common soft tissue sarcoma in children and adolescents, although rare in adults (1, 2, 3, 4).

It is most prevalent in the head and neck (35% to 50%), the genitourinary tract (25%), and the extremities (20%) (4, 5, 6). RMS of the head and neck is classified into three anatomical categories: orbital, parameningeal, and non-orbital/non-parameningeal (7, 8, 9)

Orbital RMS clinically presents with exophthalmos, altered extraocular movements, visual deficits, and pain. Its differential diagnosis includes infectious, inflammatory, and neoplastic causes (6, 7, 8, 10, 11).

Radiological imaging is key to its characterization, with magnetic resonance imaging being the method of choice due to its accuracy in soft tissues. Morphological evaluation with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) along with myogenin immunohistochemistry is sufficient to confirm the diagnosis of RMS and assign the histological subtype (12, 13, 14, 15).

Histologically, it is distinguished as embryonal, alveolar, and spindle cell/sclerosing and pleomorphic. The alveolar type is more aggressive due to gene fusions of the PAX3-FOXO1 and PAX7-FOXO1 oncoproteins, generating the malignant phenotype (5,16, 17, 18).

Lymph node involvement is common, and the prognosis depends on the subtype, size, and extent of the tumor. Treatment is multimodal and includes surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy according to risk classification (2, 4, 19, 20, 21).

We present the case of a 26-year-old primigravida woman in the second trimester of pregnancy who presented with rapidly progressive ocular proptosis, accompanied by moderate pain, blurred vision, and diplopia. Magnetic resonance imaging revealed an expansile orbital lesion that was found to be an alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma. This case is characterized by the complexity of its management, which included a multidisciplinary approach and radical surgical intervention to allow the pregnancy to continue in a young patient, and how its management was tailored to balance oncologic

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treatment with fetal health. Ethical considerations and challenges in cancer treatment during pregnancy were discussed, and the case highlights the importance of personalized and ethical management in low-incidence oncologic situations.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 26-year-old woman, primigravida, 23 weeks pregnant, with no relevant medical history. Her condition began in January 2024 with spontaneous protrusion of the right eyeball, accompanied by mild pain and signs of local inflammation, without affecting her vision at that time. Initially, the condition was considered inflammatory; however, the lesion grew rapidly, accompanied by blurred vision, diplopia, upper eyelid edema, and increasing pain intensity. She was referred to a tertiary care hospital in March 2025. Her ophthalmologic examination revealed a 26 mm proptosis in the right eye, vascular engorgement in the upper eyelid, a 9 mm lagophthalmos, hyperemic conjunctiva (++), chemosis in the lower eye, and a 2 x 2 mm conjunctival laceration in the nasal area. The cornea appeared clear, the anterior chamber well formed (Van Herick III), with clear aqueous fluid and no cellularity. The pupil was central, hyporeactive, and the lens was transparent. Fundus examination revealed engorged vessels and an elevated optic nerve with blurred, pale edges (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Right eye of the patient with the descriptions already described.

The patient underwent simple and contrast-enhanced MRI with spin echo technique, using T1-, T2-, FLAIR-, Hemo-, DWI-, ADC-, and T1-weighted sequences with gadolinium. The studies revealed an expansive, oval-shaped lesion with lobulated and heterogeneous borders, which behaved as hypointense on T1 and hyperintense on T2 and FLAIR. In addition, it presented magnetic susceptibility artifact on HEMO, restriction on DWI/ADC sequences, and intense enhancement after the administration of intravenous contrast medium. The lesion measured 3.2 x 4.9 cm in its maximum axes, generating a mass effect on the eyeball, which caused right exophthalmos. Brain structures (cerebellum, medulla oblongata, pons, and stem) with adequate morphology and signal intensity were identified in the posterior fossa, with no abnormalities in the basal cisterns or the fourth ventricle. At

the supratentorial level, adequate signal intensity was observed in the basal ganglia, subcortical and deep white matter, and cerebral cortex. No intra-axial involvement was observed (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2. Plain and contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging with spin echo technique, using T1-weighted, T2-weighted, FLAIR, Hemo, DWI, ADC, and T1-weighted sequences with gadolinium. Sagittal and axial views.

The patient underwent a biopsy, which revealed alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, with positive immunohistochemistry for desmin, MYO D1, CAM 5.2, and CD 56. Negative results included CD 99, enolase, chromogranin, synaptophysin, NUD, P63, AAML, calretinin, and PS100.

Given that this was a high-risk case, both obstetrically and oncologically, the case was discussed by the ethics committee and among the various specialties involved. A resection was proposed to continue the pregnancy and allow fetal development to viability. The decision to perform aggressive oncological treatment while maintaining the pregnancy was ethically justified through the principles of beneficence (doing good) and nonmaleficence (doing no harm). Despite the inherent risks for both mother and fetus, the intervention sought to provide the best possible outcome for both. She was evaluated by obstetrics-gynecology and maternal-fetal medicine, and induction was initiated for fetal lung maturation, with the intention of considering delivery within 5 to 6 weeks. A uterine inhibitor was also administered. The oncologic surgical procedure was initiated with a transorbital approach, performing a right ocular exenteration. The tumor was observed to be dependent on soft tissue, measuring approximately 6 cm x 8 cm x 6 cm, causing edema of the eyeball and upper and lower eyelids, with extension to the roof and floor of the orbit. Resection was performed, and a transoperative neurosurgical consultation was requested to address possible infiltration of the meninges. A right frontal craniotomy was performed, where thickening of the dura mater at the level of the extraconal space was observed, with a 7 mm orbital defect. In addition, before completing the procedure, a flap was created from the right temporalis muscle to reconstruct the orbital floor and fill the space in the orbital cavity. The procedure was completed successfully. During the procedure, fetal heart rate monitoring showed an average of 110 beats per minute (Figures 3 and 4).

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FIGURE 3. A) Transorbital approach, performing right ocular exenteration. B) Right frontal craniotomy + right temporalis muscle flap..

FIGURE 4. Right temporalis muscle flap for orbital floor reconstruction and orbital cavity space filling

The patient remained in the intensive care unit during her postoperative stay. At 28 weeks of gestation, the pregnancy was terminated abdominally, resulting in a live infant weighing 1440 g and with an APGAR score of 8-9.

Tumor histopathology revealed a unifocal alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, measuring 3.5 cm in the long axis and with characteristics consistent with the solid variant of alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma. The mitotic rate was 2, necrosis was less than 50%, and FNCLCC (Fédération Nationale des Centres de Lutte Contre le Cancer) grade 3. The surgical resection margins were in contact with the neoplasm, the optic nerve, and the ladder, with no evidence of neoplastic infiltration. FOXO1 expression was not determined by sequencing. Following evaluations by medical oncology, radiation oncology, and pathology, and based on the information obtained, the patient was classified as intermediate-risk alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, clinical group IIIB, favorable site, pT4aN0M0 according to the Clinical Oncology Group (COG) and the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC).

After termination of pregnancy, based on the group and functional status, a regimen with VAC (vincristine, actinomycin D, and cyclophosphamide) was considered due to intermediate risk. However, it was decided to start treatment with VIE (vincristine, ifosfamide, and etoposide) due to its relatively manageable toxicity profile compared to other more intensive regimens.

Currently, at 10 months, the patient is well-tolerated and in her sixth cycle, and the same regimen is being continued. Follow-up is ongoing to detect early recurrences, monitor treatment side effects, and ensure the patient's quality of life.

DISCUSSION

RMS is a high-grade malignant soft tissue tumor with skeletal muscle cell characteristics. Orbital RMS is usually observed in the first decade of life, especially between 5 and 7 years of age (6, 7).

Rarely, it invades the bony walls and adjacent paranasal sinuses. Therefore, this tumor, clearly adjacent to the skull base and its meninges, is not, due to its natural history, appropriate for inclusion in the parameningeal areas unless there is intracranial extension or significant bone invasion at the skull base. Primary locations of RMS are classified as favorable or unfavorable, with parameningeal locations being defined as unfavorable (1, 11).

The patient presented in this clinical case is outside the typical range for diagnosis, as she is a young adult who presents with the tumor in the second trimester of pregnancy, a rare circumstance that is poorly documented in the literature. This underscores the uniqueness of this case, as RMS in adults is usually located in areas such as the extremities or the genitourinary tract, but the orbital area is less common, especially in adult women. Based on its histology, it is classified into four main subtypes: embryonal (ERMS), alveolar (ARMS), spindle cell/sclerosing, and pleomorphic, each with its own histological, immunohistochemical, and molecular characteristics. ERMS is the most common subtype. One-third of cases appear in children under 5 years of age. In adults, it accounts for 20% of RMS cases. It is predominantly located in the head and neck and genitourinary tract. ARMS is the second most common RMS subtype, affecting children and young adults between 10 and 25 years of age and adults over 40 years of age. It is most frequently located in the deep soft tissues of the extremities (12, 14, 18, 19).

Alveolar RMS is uncommon; its presentation in an adult patient, especially during the second trimester of pregnancy, is extremely rare, with very few cases documented in the medical literature. The etiology remains unknown; however, there is an association between RMS and several genetic disorders, such as Li-Fraumeni syndrome, neurofibromatosis type 1, and DICER1 tumor predisposition syndrome (11).

Clinical manifestations include proptosis, ophthalmalgia, blurred vision, diplopia, eyelid edema and erythema, and visual disturbances. Parameningeal tumors can cause headache and focal neurological disturbances related to the mass effect (7).

Orbital RMS is frequently diagnosed as orbital cellulitis, and is a common cause of proptosis in children. The presence of SIRS and acute reaction factors help differentiate an infectious process (6). In this case, the patient was initially diagnosed with inflammatory disease. The lesion progressed

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rapidly, associated with blurred vision, diplopia, and upper eyelid edema, leading to referral to our unit. Rapid progression is a typical feature of RMS, causing structural and functional damage to nearby tissues. CT and MRI are important for the preoperative evaluation, staging, and follow-up of orbital RMS. CT is helpful in detecting bone involvement, and MRI for better spatial resolution, soft tissue contrast, and detection of intracranial spread. On CT, it appears as a homogeneous, well-defined mass, isodense compared to the extraocular muscles with contrast enhancement. Occasionally, erosion of adjacent bones can be observed, indicating the aggressive nature of the tumor (8,18).

On T1-weighted MRI images, the RMS demonstrates isointense signal relative to the extraocular muscles and hypointense signal relative to orbital fat. On T2-weighted images, it is hyperintense relative to the extraocular muscles and orbital fat. Bone erosion and infiltration into the paranasal sinuses and nasopharynx are possible. Areas of hemorrhage are rare but possible, especially in the alveolar and pleomorphic subtypes. This is the same feature observed in the clinical case presented, in which the lesion showed hypointense signal on T1 and hyperintense signal on T2 and FLAIR images (8, 10).

This is consistent with the histological and structural nature of the tumor, which tends to be denser on T1 due to its cellular composition and less dense on T2 due to its high water content. DWI/ADC sequences also showed restriction, which is indicative of higher cell density, since rhabdomyosarcomas are usually highly proliferating tumors. Additionally, as mentioned in the literature, it may show bone erosion and possible infiltration into the paranasal sinuses and nasopharynx. This case showed an expansile lesion generating a mass effect on the eyeball, indicating possible infiltration into nearby structures. Histologically, it is an undifferentiated tumor of small, round, blue cells (primitive cells) with skeletal muscle differentiation; it includes a classic and a solid variant (6,12).

Immunohistochemical studies are the main diagnostic strategy. Markers commonly found in RMS include antibodies against desmin (90%), muscle-specific actin, myoD1 (71–91%), and myoglobin. Myogenin (90%) is more expressed in the alveolar type than in the embryonal type. Vimentin and desmin are usually positive, but less specific, as they can be in other tumors with skeletal muscle differentiation. Myogenin and MyoD1 are myogenic transcriptional regulators that are expressed early in skeletal muscle differentiation (before desmin, actin, myoglobin, and myosin) (18).

Treatment decisions for pregnant patients with cancer should focus on patient preferences through shared decision-making, individualized care plans, and guidance from expert multidisciplinary teams. To uphold patient autonomy, it is critical to recognize that fetal well-being may depend on maternal well-being. However, patient wishes in balancing

maternal and fetal well-being may place patient autonomy in conflict with medical values, potentially jeopardizing the provider's duty of nonmaleficence and beneficence to the patient. A thorough discussion is essential, including eliciting patient preferences in light of the cancer prognosis and the potential risks and benefits of treatment strategies for both the patient and fetus (19).

Fetal lung maturation induction with corticosteroids was implemented to reduce the risk of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome, and the use of uterine suppressants was initiated to prevent premature delivery before fetal viability. This decision was made in accordance with WHO guidelines, which support the termination of pregnancy when the mother's health status requires it and when fetal viability is assured, with a low risk for the premature newborn, in addition to fetal health being monitored during the intervention (1, 21).

Stratification of RMS into risk groups is key to determining optimal treatment. The IRSG was founded in 1972. In 2000, it merged with other cooperative groups to become part of the Clinical Oncology Group Soft Tissue Sarcoma Committee (COG-STS) (4, 10).

In North America, the Children's Oncology Group incorporated three risk groups—low, intermediate, and high—based on a pretreatment clinical staging system according to the SIOP-International Union Against Cancer TNM system. T1 represents tumors limited to the compartment of origin; T2 represents tumors that extend beyond the tissue of origin; and a postoperative system established by the Intergroup Rhabdomyosarcoma Clinical Grouping System (IRSG) (11, 12, 13).

The risk stratification used by the European Paediatric Soft Tissue Sarcoma Group (EpSSG) includes four risk groups: low, standard, high and very high. It incorporates the following prognostic factors: postsurgical IRSG stage (I, II or III), age (< 10 years or ≥ 10 years), tumor size (diameter ≤ 5 cm or > 5 cm), histopathological subtype (embryonic or alveolar), location of the primary tumor (favorable or unfavorable) and lymph node stage (N0 or N1) (10). In our case, it was classified as orbital RMS, since the tumor depended on the extraocular musculature and presented as a homogeneous and well-defined soft mass lesion, which characterizes it as an extraconal lesion. Although in advanced cases and on rare occasions, this type of tumor can invade surrounding bony structures or walls, and despite being adjacent to the meninges, following the definition of orbital location, it was not included as a parameningeal lesion. Therefore, it was considered a favorable site (1, 7, 8).

Because head and neck sarcomas are generally smaller at presentation compared with sarcomas arising elsewhere, the eighth edition of the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) T classifications for this anatomic site were based on the size cutoffs used for other head and neck tumors. Given the new T classifications and the lack of data to evaluate these

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new size criteria, no tumor stage categories were proposed (21).

Based on IRSG protocols, recommended treatments for pediatric RMS include function-preserving gross total resection, systemic chemotherapy, and radiation therapy. With this multimodality treatment, the prognosis in the pediatric population varies dramatically between these histologic subtypes, with 5-year OS rates of 82% for the embryonal subtype and 53% for the alveolar subtype. Due to the extremely low incidence rate and the lack of large-scale clinical research, there is currently no consensus on whether histologic type also affects prognosis in adults. Although treatment experiences with pediatric RMS have been widely extrapolated to adults, the outcome of RMS in adults remains unsatisfactory, with a 5-year OS rate of 20.0–40.0% (3, 12, 13, 16). In adults, they can be controlled locoregionally with concurrent chemoradiotherapy, and extensive surgical resection, such as craniofacial resection and orbital exenteration, which would be necessary for many of these patients but have functional and cosmetic consequences, should be considered for treatment in this population. The main objective of surgery for RMS is to achieve complete resection of the tumor with a margin of normal tissue. This helps minimize the risk of residual cancer cells and reduces the likelihood of recurrence (14, 17).

The European approach to chemotherapy in low-risk disease is to administer eight cycles of the lower-intensity vincristine and actinomycin-D (VA). In comparison, all other RMS patients receive nine cycles of chemotherapy: patients with standard-risk disease initially receive four cycles of ifosfamide, vincristine, and actinomycin-D (IVA) and then VA in subsequent cycles; in high-risk disease, nine cycles of IVA are used. The COG-preferred VAC combination, in which ifosfamide is replaced by cyclophosphamide, is recommended only in cases with significant renal impairment (10).

In North America, for intermediate- and high-risk disease, systemic therapy for RMS is based on intensive chemotherapy with multiple alkylating agents, administered at 6- to 9-month intervals. The standard chemotherapy backbone includes vincristine, actinomycin D, and cyclophosphamide (known as VAC). Vincristine, doxorubicin, and cyclophosphamide alternating with ifosfamide and etoposide (VAC-IE) was found to be effective for patients with intermediate-risk RMS (20).

After surgery and pregnancy termination, systemic treatment was initiated with the VIE (vincristine, ifosfamide, and etoposide) regimen due to its toxicity profile, which is appropriate for the treatment of alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, in accordance with COG recommendations. This regimen was also chosen because the risk of relapse or progression is high in intermediate-risk tumors, and intensive chemotherapy is essential to improve long-term prognosis (12, 20, 21).

Due to anatomical limitations, extended radical resection is difficult to perform; therefore, RT is almost always used,

regardless of the extent of resection in the pediatric population (3).

The dose is adjusted based on the extent of prior surgical resection to reduce radiation-related sequelae, such as skeletal muscle changes. In European trials, radiation therapy is omitted under certain circumstances in an attempt to spare most patients from treatment adverse effects, provided that effective salvage therapy is available. The optimal timing of RT continues to evolve. Current COG recommendations indicate that treatment should be initiated after four cycles (12 weeks) of chemotherapy, even in patients with parameningeal involvement (16, 17, 20, 21).

Approximately 2% of patients with intermediate-risk RMS experience early disease progression, usually local failure. Delaying or omitting RT after week 24 is associated with local recurrence. Precision biologic staging and new local control techniques, such as particle therapy and brachytherapy, are being investigated with the common goal of curing RMS (6, 13).

For this patient, radiation therapy was not initially administered due to potential adverse effects on the fetus, but was planned after the patient's functional status improved. Radiation therapy in pregnant women is used more cautiously, following the recommendations of the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO), which suggest waiting until the pregnancy reaches term or terminating it (5, 6, 16, 18).

CONCLUSION

Orbital alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma is a rare malignancy in adults and even rarer in the context of pregnancy, which represents a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge. In this case, the patient presented progressive symptoms that led to the identification of an expansive lesion in the orbit, confirmed histopathologically. Surgical intervention was necessary for local control of the tumor, also allowing for obtaining an adequate sample for definitive diagnosis.

The importance of early diagnosis and a comprehensive approach is essential to improve prognosis and avoid complications arising from tumor progression.

Oncologic management in pregnant patients requires a balance between treatment effectiveness and maternal and fetal safety. In this case, multidisciplinary planning allowed for the determination of an optimal therapeutic strategy, considering orbital exenteration and subsequent initiation of chemotherapy. The medical literature suggests that, although orbital sarcomas are aggressive, the combination of surgery and chemotherapy may offer better survival rates, highlighting the need to personalize treatment based on the stage of the disease and the patient's condition. Finally, this report underscores the importance of evidence-based decision-making tailored to exceptional clinical situations, such as cancer during pregnancy. Collaboration between oncologists, surgeons, obstetricians, and maternal-fetal medicine specialists is essential to optimize outcomes.

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Despite the rarity of these tumor types, the documentation and analysis of these cases contribute to the development of clinical guidelines that will improve diagnosis and management in similar future scenarios.

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